

Table 1. Performance of Liangyou Peite in South China and Hunan provincial and regional trials.

Character	South China		Hunan	
	1991	1992	1992	1993
	Mid 23 sites, 10 provinces	Late 12 sites, 8 provinces	Mid 7 sites	Mid 6 sites
Growth duration (d)	143.0	125.9	136.7	135.8
Growth duration (d) over check	-1.5	-3.4	-3.0	-5.5
Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	6.2 ^a	6.7	9.5	7.7
Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹) over check	1.6 ^b	8.9 ^c	4.7 ^{bd}	5.8 ^b
Basic tillers (no. m ⁻²)	99.0	-	145.5	136.5
Maximum tillers (no. m ⁻²)	478.5	-	559.5	603.0
Productive panicles (no. m ⁻²)	288	317	333	333
Spikelets (no. panicle ⁻¹)	157.8	132.6	140.1	144.5
Filled grains (no. panicle ⁻¹)	118.6	100.8	126.2	122.3
Seed set (%)	75.2	76.0	87.9	84.6
1,000-grain weight (g)	22.8	23.1	23.4	22.3
Plant height (cm)	101	93	98	106

^aBrown rice yield. ^bCheck is Shanyou 63 (three-line rice hybrid). ^cCheck is Shanyou Gui 99 (three-line rice hybrid).
^dSignificant at the 1% level.

Table 2. Grain quality of Liangyou Peite.

Grain length (mm)	5.28
Grain width (mm)	2.35
Length-width ratio	2.30
Chalky grain (%)	80.0
Chalky area (%)	5.3
Brown rice (%)	83.8
Milled rice (%)	75.9
Head rice (%)	60.0
Gelatinization temperature (°C)	4.8
Gel consistency (mm)	30
Amylose content (%)	22.4
Protein content (%)	10.3
Eating quality	Good
Remark on quality	Fine

for making indica and japonica hybrid rices. The male parent Teqing is a high-yielding inbred indica variety.

The seed yield of Pei' Ai 64 S averaged more than 3.0 t ha⁻¹ with a maximum of 5.5 t ha⁻¹. F₁ hybrid seed yield was 2.3-3.0 t ha⁻¹ in Hunan in 1995. ■

Khushboo, a quality rice cultivar for Rajasthan

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BK-805-36, a cross derived from Baran Basmati/Pusa 150, has been released as Khushboo in Rajasthan, India. It was identified in the F₆ generation at ARS, Kota.

Khushboo is a semidwarf cultivar that matures in 118-123 d when transplanted. It is suitable for either normal or late sowing and possesses ideal plant type with upright leaves, compact tillering, late leafsenescence, and horizontal flag leaf position. Panicles are long (28 cm), compact, and fully exerted. Spikelets are partially awned and straw colored. Kernels are 7.5 mm with a length-breadth ratio of 4.7.

Table 1. Performance of Khushboo in varietal trials. Kota, Rajasthan, India. 1986-91.

Year	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)		CD (0.05)
	Khushboo	Basmati 370 (check)	
1986	3.4	2.6	0.4
1987	3.5	2.8	0.5
1988	2.9	2.1	0.3
1989	2.7	2.3	0.5
1990	3.5	3.0	0.3
1991	4.0	3.4	0.4
Average	3.3	2.7	
Percent over Basmati 370	23.9		

Kernel length after cooking is 13.4 mm with an elongation ratio of 1.8. The grains are long and slender, white, translucent, and strongly scented. Cooked rice is soft and well separated.

In trials conducted at Kota from 1986 to 1991, Khushboo yielded consistently higher than Basmati 370 (Table 1). In coordinated trials conducted during 1989 at 11 locations and in 1990 at 7 locations, Khushboo yielded 14.7 and 9.17% more than Basmati 370, respectively. In on-farm demonstrations conducted, Khushboo yielded 41% in 1991 and 54% higher than Basmati 370 (Table 2).

The cultivar is resistant to leaf blast and sheath rot, and moderately resistant to neck blast, brown spot, and white-backed plantopper. ■

Table 2. Khushboo grain yield in on-farm demonstrations. Kota, Rajasthan, India. 1991-92.

Year	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	
	Khushboo	Basmati 370 (check)
1991 (4 locations)	4.9	3.5
Percent over Basmati 370	41	
1992 (7 locations)	3.9	2.5
Percent over Basmati 370	54	

Bright-pearl 1, a fast grain-filling japonica rice

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All of the traditional late-japonica rice cultivars grown in the Yangtze River area of China require 45-50 d from heading to ripening. Sometimes the grain-filling period is longer because of unfavorable weather, resulting in low rice yield and delayed sowing of the next crop. Local farmers normally choose early-ripening rice cultivars. But the plants usually have insufficient growing time.

With a longer vegetative stage and a fast grain-filling rate, the late-japonica rice can be harvested in late October instead of early November, thus avoiding inclement weather and reducing moldy or sprouted seed. Using a fast grain-filling cultivar can increase rice quality. The ability to supply the market early means a better price for growers.

Bright-pearl 1, derived from Bin 8103/713 in 1992, is a fast grain-filling japonica rice. Its grain filling is 10-15 d faster than that of check Xiushui 11. Bin 8103 is an early ripening/japonica cultivar resistant to brown planthopper (BPH) and blast. 713 is

Table 1. The major agronomic characters of Bright-pearl 1.

Site	Sowing (month/day)	Planting method ^a	80% heading (month/day)	Growth duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	Seed set (%)	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)
Hangzhou, Zhejiang	7/8	TP	9/18	112	85.2	69.9	88.6	7.64
	7/15	BS	9/19	107	82.5	72.8	83.2	6.95
	6/16	DS	8/24	106	89.7	62.6	92.3	7.25
	7/10	DS	9/14	96	85.9	65.1	86.7	6.81
	7/25	DS	9/24	92	81.5	64.2	84.7	6.43
Jiaxing, Zhejiang	7/10	BS	9/11	103	87.5	77.2	85.6	6.48
Ningbo, Zhejiang	6/20	TP	9/3	115	90.2	76.5	89.5	8.21
Tanzhou, Zhejiang	7/10	TP	9/15	107	84.6	78.9	84.3	7.82
Dangtu, Aihui	6/24	TP	9/2	106	87.0	71.6	85.1	7.13
Nanlin, Aihui	6/30	TP	9/15	120	92.7	74.6	91.2	7.50
Jinshan, Shanghai	5/27	TP	8/25	136	98.0	78.0	89.7	7.13
Nantong, Jiangsu	5/20	TP	8/25	133	95.4	71.4	93.4	6.69
Xingfeng, Jiangxi	6/30	DS	9/5	105	99.5	80.5	94.3	9.99

^aTP = transplanting, BS = broadcast seeding, DS = direct sowing.

Table 2. Milled rice properties of Bright-pearl 1.

Variety	Length (mm)	Width (mm)	Shape L/W	Chalkiness (%)	1000-grain weight (g)	Alkali spreading value	Amylose content	Unbroken milled rice (%)
Bright-pearl 1	4.9	2.9	1.7	0.5	26.2	6.7	16.3	75.9
Xiushui 11 (check)	5.3	3.0	1.7	7.0	27.5	7.0	15.6	64.7

a late japonica cultivar that resists bacterial blight (BB) and blast. Bright-pearl 1 is a photoperiod-sensitive japonica rice with blast, BB, and BPH resistance. Its growth duration is about 135 d for a single crop and about 100 d for late season direct sowing in Zhejiang, Aihui, and Shanghai.

The major agronomic characters were recorded (Table 1). Bright-pearl 1 has ideal plant type, with erect leaves, suitable stem angles, a strong root system, and tolerance for lodging. It also has good rice quality (Table 2). Bright-pearl 1 can be used in japonica rice breeding and can be planted by farmers. ■

Crop and resource management

Physiology and plant nutrition

Growth characteristics of IRRI-developed new rice plant type breeding lines in Japan

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IRRI recently developed breeding lines of a new rice plant type (NPT) that promises increased yield potential in the tropics. These lines are tropical japonicas that have fewer but larger panicles than current modern varieties. They are known as panicle weight types. The physiological basis for the increased yield of the lines, however, has not been elucidated.

We conducted field experiments at NARC to examine the factors related to the

yield potential of these NPT lines. Two NPT lines provided by IRRI and four cultivars (Table 1) were transplanted in 1994 during mid-May and mid-June. Planting density was 26.7 hills m⁻² and 180 kg N ha⁻¹ was applied (80 kg as basal, 60 kg at panicle initiation, and 40 kg during mid-reproductive phase). Standard management practices were followed.

The dry weight of each organ and the leaf area were monitored at three growth stages for 15 plants. Yield and its components were observed in three replicated plots. The average solar radiation and average temperature during the growing season were higher than normal, contributing to good growth. Damage from disease and insect pests was minimal. Necrosis of the axis of the panicle and rachis in IR66740-ACI-3 plants was observed during the late ripening phase.

The NPT lines grew slowly initially, but the rate during the reproductive phase was faster than that of the other cultivars. Dry weight at heading was almost the same for

the test materials, although it was sometimes higher for the NPT lines. However, the biological yield of the NPT lines was lower than that of most of the cultivars because the increase in their dry weight after heading was lower. Panicle number of the NPT lines was low, and IR65598-112-2 was the lowest. The spikelet number panicle⁻¹ of IR65598-112-2 was the highest among the materials tested (Table 1).

Leaves of both NPT lines were erect during the ripening phase, which ensured better canopy structure. No lodging was observed in NPT lines although most of the other cultivars from both plantings lodged during the mid-ripening phase (Table 1).

Sink size was calculated by multiplying filled grain weight by spikelet number. No significant difference was found between the sink size of the NPT lines and most of the cultivars, although their economic yield was the lowest due to a lower grain-filling percentage (Table 2).

The reduced percentage of filled grains was attributed to the grain sink being